

REVIEWER'S REPORT

**Manuscript Number: ID QSS-2025-0004 entitled
"Questionable Authorship Practices or Questionable Methodology?
A Critique of "Using Bibliometrics to Detect Questionable Authorship and
Affiliation Practices and Their Impact on Global Research Metrics: A Case
Study of 14 Universities"**

This paper questions the results obtained in the recently published article in *Quantitative Science Studies* (https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00339) entitled "Using Bibliometrics to Detect Questionable Authorship and Affiliation Practices and Their Impact on Global Research Metrics: A Case Study of 14 Universities". It argues that there are significant methodological flaws that undermine the reliability of its findings and limit its validity. The following issues are highlighted:

- A. Sampling Bias: Arbitrary thresholds and restrictive criteria exclude relevant data and skew findings.
- B. Inappropriate Control Group: The study compares institutions with vastly different academic contexts, introducing confounding variables.
- C. Correlation Without Causation: The authors rely on descriptive statistics to imply unethical behavior without substantiating causal links.

In my view, the critical value of the letter presented here is debatable because:

- It provides an analysis redundant with the comments already made by Reviewer 1¹.
- It is based on a flawed axiom: that the study suffers from sampling problems, despite it being a case study whose findings can only be extrapolated to the 14 universities analyzed, something explicitly stated in the article's title.
- It raises uncertain criticisms regarding the reliability and validity of the findings (confusing sampling technique with validity, unjustified questioning of reliability, and mixing up internal validity with external validity).

It appears that the objective of this letter is to methodologically discredit this work in order to "clear" the reputations of the institutions included in this case study, which, according to the author of the letter, are "simply experiencing rapid growth, which could be driven by legitimate factors unrelated to questionable authorship practices, such as increased faculty hiring, research funding, or specialization in rapidly advancing fields" However, what remains indisputable here, because it is supported by irrefutable data, is that these 14 universities exhibit highly anomalous patterns in publication output, authorship, and affiliation practices, raising serious concerns regarding the integrity of their published research.

A. Redundant revision

¹ Available at: https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/10.1162%2Fqss_a_00339?type=doi

In essence, this letter is largely redundant with the peer review already conducted for this article during the journal's review process, particularly concerning the suggestions, comments, and criticisms made by the first reviewer². The peer review previously identified as critical elements: the selection of the studied institutions, the use of a "control group" for comparison purposes, and the interpretation of the results. Many of these comments were addressed by the authors and incorporated into the final manuscript, particularly through an extensive section explicitly detailing the study's limitations. These limitations clearly establish the boundaries, scope, and methodological shortcomings of the research, precisely the aspects addressed in this letter.

B. Sampling in a case study

The letter starts from a mistaken premise: by definition, a case study does not constitute a representative sample, as probabilistic methods are not employed in selecting cases. The article's title explicitly states that this is "**A Case Study of 14 Universities**", clearly indicating that the conclusions drawn are only applicable to the institutions analyzed.

This issue was raised by the first reviewer of the article. In response, the authors revised the title of the paper, explicitly including the term "case study" and specifying precisely the number of universities to which this study is limited. This adjustment prevents misinterpretations.

This idea is emphasized throughout the article, as evidenced by the main objective stated in the abstract: "We employed bibliometric analysis to examine shifts in authorship and affiliation dynamics **at these** universities", and similarly in the introduction: "we examine **14 universities** that demonstrate significant anomalies in research output and authorship and affiliation patterns".

Therefore, there is no issue regarding sample representativeness or generalizability of the results, as this study does not aim to achieve that. Such representativeness is unnecessary to demonstrate the utility of bibliometric indicators in detecting anomalous patterns in publication output, authorship, and affiliation practices.

Moreover, from a strictly methodological perspective, sample randomness can never affect the "validity of the findings", only the generalizability or extrapolation of the results.

When opting for a case study, researchers obviously choose a non-probabilistic sampling method. In such scenarios, the critical issue is to justify, through logical and rigorous arguments, the criteria used for selecting the cases, always aligned with the objectives of the study. All decisions made in selecting the universities analyzed here are very well justified.

C. Selection of the institutions included in the case study

- The letter criticizes the use of a selection threshold of universities that published more than 2000 publications between 2019 and 2023, arguing that it introduces "significant sampling biases into their analysis". However, the threshold employed is fully justified, as this study specifically aims to

² https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/10.1162%2Fqss_a_00339?type=doi

analyze institutions with substantial influence on global ranking metrics. Moreover, in institutional bibliometric analyses, it is common practice to use a productivity threshold to focus on institutions with substantial research output, thereby avoiding variability and instability issues associated with smaller publication counts.

- Can selecting universities exhibiting increases in publication output exceeding 100% be considered unjustified as a selection threshold? Certainly, the chosen threshold is arbitrary (it could have been set at 50% or 150%), but the criterion itself is reasonable and appropriate for identifying unquestionable indicators of anomalous publication patterns. Increasing publication output at a rate five times higher than the global average is “extraordinary” and clearly beyond normal expectations.
- Is it unfounded to select institutions that also exhibited declines in rates of first authorship greater than 15 percentage points, over five times the world average? The critical issue is not whether the threshold used to select the universities is arbitrary, but rather the significant drop itself. Such a pronounced decrease is highly abnormal, especially when occurring rapidly and alongside exponential growth in publication numbers. Clearly, this represents another strong indicator that something unusual is happening in the production of published knowledge at these institutions. Furthermore, the criticism regarding the exclusive focus on first authorship while neglecting the roles of last and/or corresponding authorship is questionable. It is widely recognized that first authors generally bear primary responsibility and play a crucial role in conducting the research and writing the articles. This fact is supported by the common practice in which the corresponding author typically coincides with the first author, far more frequently than with the last author.
- The selected time window is appropriate for the study's purpose: observing abrupt changes within very short periods. Experiencing extreme growth in the number of publications, authorship and affiliation practices, and rapid changes in university rankings within such a brief timeframe (five years) is a clear indication of severe anomalies in how published scientific knowledge is produced. Indeed, a five-year timeframe is commonly used in bibliometrics to detect short-term shifts and trends.
- The criticism regarding the inconsistency in using the 2019–2024 time window for the number of hyper-prolific authors (Table 4), instead of the 2019–2023 window consistently applied throughout the rest of the study, is justified.
- Certainly, the COVID-19 pandemic, which spanned the central years of the study, may have influenced publication behaviors, and indeed, we know this has occurred. However, since this was a global pandemic, one would need to demonstrate that the countries hosting the studied institutions experienced changes in publication patterns that were distinctly different or more extreme than elsewhere. Can the critics empirically show that phenomena substantially different from the global trend occurred in these specific countries?

D. Use of a control group

I agree with the criticism regarding the use of the control group: “Questionable Control Group: The selection of Caltech, MIT, Princeton, and UC Berkeley as a

control group is highly problematic. These elite institutions differ significantly from the Middle Eastern and South Asian universities under study in terms of funding, resources, disciplinary focus, and academic culture”.

This text aligns with the observation previously made by Reviewer 1³:

“The use of what the authors refer to as the "control group" is problematic for two reasons:

- Its use is incorrect. The term "control group" is not being used in its canonical research sense: a group similar to the study group. The 16 selected universities cannot be compared with the 7 included in the control group simply because they differ in many variables that can bias the results (a comparison of the two groups in Table 1 is sufficient to see this). What do 16 universities from various countries in the Middle East have in common with 7 universities from the United States, Switzerland, and Hong Kong? The results of this comparison could be affected by differences in the institutional profiles of the universities (age, public or private status, size, degree of specialization...). A thematic analysis in Scopus, Web of Science, SciVal, or InCites of the universities chosen for the study would be enough to observe the differences in the weight of various disciplines. This issue is important because authorship practices are dependent on the field of knowledge.

- It is not necessary to use a randomized or conveniently selected control group here according to the basic characteristics of the analyzed institutions. Comparison with the global average is more robust in terms of internal validity (confidence in detecting anomalies in the studied variables) and external validity of the results (potential degree of generalization). However, I believe it would be very relevant to compare the results of the analyzed institutions with the national average. Including bibliometric data from the country is relevant to check if there are decisive contextual factors (national legislation, the country's scientific culture, incentive system). National deviations, not just institutional ones, might be detected, which would be an interesting result of this study”

In response, the authors included a specific statement within the limitations section of their study explicitly acknowledging the comparability and interpretative issues, and providing justification for their use:

“The control group of globally renowned institutions was selected to provide a stable reference point. However, differences between the study and control groups regarding institutional age, size, funding, and governance must be noted. These differences may influence the interpretation of the findings. Nevertheless, the control group offered a high-standard baseline for assessing deviations in research and authorship trends”

³ https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/10.1162%2Fqss_a_00339?type=doi

I find the instrumental reasons provided to justify the use of the control group convincing. Given that many of the 14 studied universities have managed to rapidly climb to top positions in global rankings, rankings based on publication metrics, it is valuable to compare them with institutions at their "supposedly equivalent level". This comparison makes it easier to highlight the anomalous patterns exhibited by these institutions relative to others characterized by stable behaviors and recognized as global benchmarks in research.

Moreover, introducing national-level comparisons effectively provided context for the institutions and allowed for more precise calibration of the deviations exhibited by each university.

E. Reliability and validity of the study

The question that could genuinely challenge this study is whether the methods employed are reliable (they consistently measure the analyzed variables) and whether the results obtained are valid.

The criticisms presented in this letter do not affect the reliability or validity of the findings. The variables analyzed in this study have been accurately measured: substantial increases in publication output, decreased first authorship rates, rise in hyper-prolific authors, increases in multi-affiliated publications, and growth in authorship per publication. The abrupt transformations identified clearly reflect highly unusual, anomalous patterns in publication, authorship, and affiliation practices, raising justified suspicions.

However, the letter correctly points out that these results do not empirically demonstrate unethical behavior. There is a crucial difference between suggesting questionable practices and confirming them as established facts, a distinction previously emphasized by Reviewer 1, whose critique led to changes in all relevant statements throughout the study.

F. Lack of causal analysis and alternative explanations

The author of this letter is correct when pointing out that this study does not establish a causal relationship between the anomalous publication patterns observed and the existence of questionable authorship practices.

This criticism had already been raised by Reviewer 1:

“However, what is not demonstrated in this study is the existence of gift, honorary, and sold authorship, as suggested in the abstract and conclusions. There are no data or empirical evidence clearly showing that gift, honorary, and sold authorship have occurred. To achieve this, the analysis must be taken down to the level of individual authors: the authorship practices of the researchers responsible for these deviations must be studied to identify illogical behaviors. Once these are identified, the responsible authors need to be interviewed directly to understand the motivations behind their behaviors. In the case of sold authorship, the most robust procedure is to find specific advertisements in various online spaces where these sales occur. I encourage the authors to take this step. Only in this way will fraudulent behaviors be clarified, and those responsible can be identified.

In short, what this reviewer wants to emphasize is that while this is a very plausible interpretation inferred or derived from the data, it is not a scientifically proven fact in this study. Therefore, it should be stressed that it is an interpretation, explanation, or hypothesis that must be tested against reality”

In response to these observations, the authors acknowledged the error in their approach and revised "the abstract, presentation, discussion, and conclusion to clarify that the mention of gift, honorary, and sold authorship is speculative rather than confirmed, clearly distinguishing between suggesting possible explanations and establishing proven facts."

The study conclusively demonstrates deviations in publication, authorship, and affiliation practices at the analyzed institutions. It reveals clear anomalies in these patterns. Although empirical proof of intent or unethical behavior is not established, it is reasonable and justified to suggest that such practices could be intended to artificially boost publication metrics, given their alignment with previously documented anomalies in the scientific literature and widely reported concerns regarding questionable practices in international media. This interpretation aligns with numerous documented cases in existing literature, as well as with anomalies previously identified by scientific studies on the subject.

Years ago, the strategy employed by Saudi universities to improve their positions in publication and citation-based university rankings was uncovered. Recently, specific details about how this system operated have come to light. Given that one of the ranking factors is based on publication and citation metrics, Saudi universities systematically incentivized highly cited authors to affiliate their publications with them.

Bhattacharjee, Y. (2011). Saudi universities offer cash in exchange for academic prestige. *Science*, 334(6061): 1344-1345. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.334.6061.1344>

Ansele, M. (2023). One of the world's most cited scientists, Rafael Luque, suspended without pay for 13 years. *El País*, <https://english.elpais.com/science-tech/2023-04-02/one-of-the-worlds-most-cited-scientists-rafael-luque-suspended-without-pay-for-13-years.html>

Ansele, M. (2023). Saudi Arabia pays Spanish scientists to pump up global university rankings. *El País*, <https://english.elpais.com/science-tech/2023-04-18/saudi-arabia-pays-spanish-scientists-to-pump-up-global-university-rankings.html>

Ansele, M. (2024). Dozens of the world's most cited scientists stop falsely claiming to work in Saudi Arabia. *El País*, <https://english.elpais.com/science-tech/2024-12-05/dozens-of-the-worlds-most-cited-scientists-stop-falsely-claiming-to-work-in-saudi-arabia.html>

Catanzaro, M. (2023). Saudi universities entice top scientists to switch affiliations. *Nature*, 617, 5 May 2023. <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-023-01523-x>

These practices have also been documented in India:

<https://retractionwatch.com/2023/12/21/exclusive-researcher-outs-indian-universitys-publishing-scam-after-it-fails-to-pay-him/>

On the culture of manipulating metrics to climb rankings in India, we have the recent work of

Agrawal, A., & Koley, M. (2024). Are the Metrics being Gamed? A Closer Look at the Rise and Fall of Universities in NIRF 2024 Rankings. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13350313>

In very recent studies on the global geography of article retractions, Iraq, Saudi Arabia, and India have been identified among the countries with the highest article retraction rates. Several of the universities included in this study (King Saud, Taif, King Abdulaziz) are also among those with the highest number of retractions.

“In India, it’s notable that the institutes with the highest retraction rates are almost all private colleges and institutes in the state of Tamil Nadu, an education hub, says Achal Agrawal (...) Private institutions, he says, push students and researchers to publish many articles, and in some cases pay bonuses for papers published (...) In recent years, some private institutes have climbed national rankings of research standings by massively expanding their publication and citation records — but they also have high retraction numbers and rates. “I think we need to push for retractions to be taken into account for rankings,” Agrawal says. “It’s the only language that the institutes understand.”

Van Noorden, R. (2025). Exclusive: These universities have the most retracted scientific articles. *Nature*, 638(8051), 596-599.

Comments in a Retraction Watch post about the work reveal a shared concern that the pressure to publish in these institutions can lead some researchers to adopt questionable publication practices.

<https://retractionwatch.com/2025/01/10/bibliometrics-universities-publication-metrics-authorship/>

Additionally, a study on the geography of extremely prolific authors revealed that “The largest fold-wise increases between 2016 and 2022 (5-19-fold) occurred in Thailand, Saudi Arabia, Spain, India, Italy, Russia, Pakistan, and South Korea.”

Ioannidis, J.P.A., Collins, T.A. & Baas, J. Evolving patterns of extreme publishing behavior across science. *Scientometrics* 129, 5783–5796 (2024).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-024-05117-w>

Given the evidence presented in this study, it is reasonable to consider that questionable authorship practices might be occurring. While alternative explanations, such as increased research funding, greater co-authorship collaboration, or multi-affiliation practices, could also contribute to higher publication outputs, these factors do not fully account for the sudden and marked

changes observed. The evidence from other studies serves as an indication that such malpractices exist, and therefore, it is plausible to hypothesize that similar issues could be present in the universities analyzed here, based on the anomalous patterns noted. However, this remains a hypothesis that requires further investigation.